

MOTIVATION AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG FACULTY OF NEGROS ORIENTAL STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This study examined faculty motivation and job satisfaction at Negros Oriental State University, investigating their relationship with socio-demographic factors to ensure quality education and meet accreditation requirements. Faculty motivation is essential in shaping future generations, yet studies indicate that educators in developing countries face low job satisfaction due to various challenges (Michaelowa, 2002). Employee satisfaction significantly impacts faculty retention, productivity, and overall institutional success (Tack & Patitu, 1992). A descriptive survey research design was employed to gather data through a structured questionnaire. The study involved regular faculty members and employed purposive sampling. The questionnaire assessed socio-demographic characteristics, motivation, and job satisfaction. The researcher adapted this study from the Teacher Motivation Questionnaire developed by the Iwate Chapter of the Japan Association of Language Teachers. At the same time, the researcher derived the job satisfaction measures from the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities of the Philippines (AACUP) Area II Faculty Instrument. Responses were analyzed using weighted mean, standard deviation, and ordinal logistic regression. The findings indicate that faculty motivation influences recognition, job security, and professional development opportunities. Job satisfaction is associated with workload, salary, benefits, faculty development, and institutional culture. Results show a significant correlation between faculty motivation and job satisfaction, aligning with previous studies (Yaya et al., 2016; Khan & Parveen, 2014). Younger faculty members demonstrated stronger motivation when presented with career opportunities. The study emphasized the significance of cultivating a supportive work environment to boost faculty motivation and

job satisfaction, ultimately enhancing institutional performance and enriching student learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Faculty Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Negros Oriental State University, Quantitative Research, Dumaguete City*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a major contributor to a country's intellectual power. The progress of a country depends upon the quality of its education, and the quality of education depends upon the quality of its faculty. The faculty is the most important element in any educational program (Thakur, 2014). As the backbone of any management institute, faculty members possess the influence and ability to shape the country's next generation (Shetty & Gujarathi, 2012). Faculty should be well prepared to do the job effectively and efficiently (Thakur, 2014). This can also be done by motivating faculty members serving the institution.

While faculty motivation is essential to teaching and learning, research indicates that many faculty members in developing countries experience low motivation. Michaelowa's (2002) study found that several factors had a detrimental impact on teacher's job satisfaction and motivation. The university should take this data seriously and investigate to achieve its goals.

One of the many challenges in retaining any workforce is employee satisfaction. Within higher education, faculty satisfaction is imperative to retention and productivity (Tack & Patitu, 1992). Retaining faculty is important for institutions because they provide numerous benefits, such as mentorship, and act as role models for minority students (Turner & Myers, 2000). Thus, understanding faculty job satisfaction is a significant factor for institutional success.

The most important information regarding an employee in an organization is a validated measure of his/her level of job satisfaction (Roznowski & Hulin, 1992). A better understanding of job satisfaction and its factors helps guide employees' activities in a desired direction. For example, job satisfaction is significantly linked to factors like employee motivation and performance (Ostroff, 1992) and turnover (Griffeth et al., 2000) and even positively influence organizational behaviour (Organ and Ryan, 1995).

Researchers in other countries have conducted several studies on motivation and job satisfaction. Nonetheless, the lack of current studies in the Philippines, particularly in state universities and colleges, prompted the researchers to conduct this study. The study aims to determine the motivation and job satisfaction among faculty members of Negros Oriental State University system and their relationship to the socio-demographic characteristics in order to ensure quality education within the institution. Furthermore, this also complies with the requirements of the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines for accreditation.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine the motivation and job satisfaction of the faculty of Negros Oriental State University system.

The specific problems that this study sought to answer are as follows:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the faculty in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.1 Sex;
 - 1.1 Marital Status;
 - 1.1 Academic Qualification; and
 - 1.1 Length of Service.
2. What are the factors that determine faculty motivation in terms of:
 - 2.1 Internal Factors;
 - 2.1.1 Autonomy;
 - 2.1.2 Competence;
 - 2.1.3 Curiosity;
 - 2.1.4 Love of Learning;
 - 2.1.5 Critical Thinking;
 - 2.1.6 Self-Efficacy;
 - 2.1.7 Belongingness;
 - 2.1.8 Collaboration;
 - 2.1.9 Recognition; and
 - 2.1.10 Achievement.
 - 2.2 External Factors;
 - 2.2.1 Salary;
 - 2.2.2 Contract;
 - 2.2.3 Workplace Conditions;
 - 2.2.4 Class Size;
 - 2.2.5 Academic Level;
 - 2.2.6 Discipline;
 - 2.2.6 Student Participation;
 - 2.2.6 Assessment; and
 - 2.2.6 Evaluation.
 - 2.2.6 Interpersonal Relationship
3. What is the level of job satisfaction among the faculty in terms of:
 - 3.1 Faculty Workload;
 - 3.2 Rank and Tenure;
 - 3.3 Salary and Benefits;
 - 3.4 Faculty Development; and
 - 3.5 Institution's Culture and Values.
4. How is the individual demographic profile of the faculty related to motivation and job satisfaction?
5. To what extent is motivation related to faculty job satisfaction?

METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive survey research design to obtain information for quantitative information. The researchers adopted a quantitative survey in which data was collected from a population using a purposive sampling method. The researchers used a questionnaire to collect data, which contained questions on the socio-demographic profile of the faculty, motivation, and job satisfaction. This study involved the population of regular faculty members of Negros Oriental State University.

The researchers distributed the questionnaires along with a copy of the permission letter. Respondents were also provided with a written guarantee ensuring the confidentiality of the information in the questionnaire. The demographics questions should include gender, age, marital status, academic qualification, and length of service.

The Iwate Association of Language Teachers' Teacher Motivation Questionnaire served as the model for the motivational questions, and the questionnaire was designed to identify the various factors that motivate faculty members. The questionnaire used the following five response choices with its corresponding point rating scale:

- Strongly Agree (SA) 5
- Agree (A) 4
- Neither Agree/ Neither Disagree (NA/ND) 3
- Disagree (D) 2
- Strongly Disagree (SD) 1

On the other hand, the Job Satisfaction questions were drawn from the Area II (Faculty) Instrument of the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities of the Philippines (AACUP). The questionnaire was designed to determine the faculty's job satisfaction level. The questionnaire used the following five response choices with its corresponding point rating scale:

- Extremely Satisfied (ES) 5
- Very Satisfied (VS) 4
- Satisfied (S) 3
- Somewhat Satisfied (SS) 2
- Not Satisfied (NS) 1

The reliability analysis was conducted on all questionnaire items using Cronbach's α coefficient, a measure of internal consistency that assesses how well a set of items captures a single latent construct. The acceptable range for Cronbach's α coefficient is between 0.7 and 1.0. Additionally, the reliability of each subscale will be computed to ensure consistency across different dimensions of the questionnaire.

The researchers used descriptive statistics to describe the basic features of the data in the study. Weighted mean and standard deviation were also used to summarise the sample and the measures. Multivariate statistics were applied. A multivariate analysis was performed using ordinal logistic regression to test the study's conceptual framework. Ordinal logistic regression was specifically used when the dependent variable is on an

ordinal scale (e.g., Likert scale) while independent variables are either categorical or continuous. It also investigated the relationship between motivation and faculty job satisfaction.

After retrieving the questionnaires from the individual respondents, the researchers tallied the data and used appropriate statistical tools. Then, tables and graphs were used to display the data.

The main instrument for data gathering is the survey questionnaire. Part I provided background information on the faculty. Part II focused on the faculty's motivating factors. Lastly, Part III focused on the faculty's level of job satisfaction in terms of workload, rank and tenure, salary and benefits, faculty development, and the instructor's culture and values.

RESULTS

Presented below are the findings of the study conducted on the Motivation and Job Satisfaction Among Faculty of Negros Oriental State University after the gathered data were treated with the appropriate statistical tools suited for the proper interpretation and analysis.

Table 1. Background of the Respondents

Variables	N	%
Age		
61 and above	5	5.68
56 – 60	6	6.82
51 – 55	6	6.82
46 – 50	9	10.23
41 – 45	9	10.23
36 – 40	22	25.00
31 – 35	18	20.45
26 – 30	12	13.64
20 – 25	1	1.14
Sex		
Male	32	36.36
Female	56	63.64
Marital Status		
Single	28	31.82
Married	58	65.91
Widow/Widower	1	1.14
Separated	1	1.14
Academic Qualification		
Bachelor's Degree	17	19.32
Master's Degree	40	45.45
Doctoral Degree	30	34.09

Others, please. specify	1	1.14
Length of Service		
31 and above years	4	4.55
26 – 30 years	4	4.55
21 – 25 years	5	5.68
16 – 20 years	8	9.09
11 – 15 years	17	19.32
6 – 10 years	24	27.27
1 – 5 years	26	29.55

N= 88

Table 2. Factors that determine faculty motivation

	SD	Wx	Verbal Descriptions
Internal Factors			
1. I feel that I have the freedom to make my own choices about my teaching.	.77	4.23	Strongly Agree
2. I feel that I have the professional competence to teach effectively.	.52	4.53	Strongly Agree
3. I take an interest in many ongoing experiences and find different topics and subjects interesting.	.63	4.38	Strongly Agree
4. I like to master new skills, topics, and bodies of knowledge.	.57	4.55	Strongly Agree
5. I can change my mind in light of new evidence and try to weigh all evidence fairly.	.54	4.44	Strongly Agree
6. I am confident in my ability to complete tasks and reach goals.	.62	4.41	Strongly Agree
7. I feel that I am an accepted, contributing member of the academic institution in which I work.	.75	4.30	Strongly Agree
8. I collaborate professionally with other members of the academic institution in which I work.	.59	4.47	Strongly Agree
9. I feel that I am recognized for my professional contributions in the academic institution in which I work.	.88	4.84	Strongly Agree
10. I feel a sense of achievement and award in the work that I do within the academic institution in which I work.	.81	3.89	Agree
External Factors			
1. My salary is adequate for the job that I am doing.	.96	3.61	Agree
2. I have a job security.	.84	4.24	Strongly Agree
3. The workplace conditions meet the needs of my teaching.	.84	3.61	Agree

4. The sizes of my classes are within the acceptable range of classes in my field.	.94	3.57	Agree
5. The academic level of my students is within the acceptable range of my teaching field.	.81	3.89	Agree
6. The level of discipline in my classes is within the norm in my field.	.61	4.11	Agree
7. Students participate actively in my class.	.83	3.86	Agree
8. It is important to have institutionally-mandated assessment of the students.	.60	4.15	Agree
9. Assessing faculty helps to increase their efficacy.	.75	4.20	Strongly Agree
10. I have strong relationships in my workplace, and I feel accepted by my colleagues.	.61	4.47	Strongly Agree

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Verbal Descriptions
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree
3	2.60 – 3.39	Neither Agree/Disagree
2	1.80 – 2.59	Strongly Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Satisfied

Table 3. Level of job satisfaction

	SD	Wx	Verbal Descriptions
Faculty Workload			
		2.71	
1. The faculty-student ratio is strictly followed.	1.02	3.14	Satisfied
2. The faculty schedule has time for lesson preparation.	1.11	3.22	Satisfied
3. The faculty schedule contains sufficient time for research.	1.16	2.31	Somewhat Satisfied
4. The faculty schedule contains sufficient time for extension.	1.08	2.38	Somewhat Satisfied
5. The faculty schedule contains sufficient time for production.	1.06	2.48	Somewhat Satisfied
		3.32	
Rank Tenure			
1. The faculty-student ratio is strictly followed.	1.04	3.45	Very Satisfied

2. The faculty schedule has time for lesson preparation.	1.00	3.33	Satisfied
3. The faculty schedule contains sufficient time for research.	1.12	3.50	Very Satisfied
4. The faculty schedule contains sufficient time for extension.	1.08	3.14	Satisfied
5. The faculty schedule contains sufficient time for production.	.96	3.16	Satisfied
Salary and Benefits		3.18	
1. The regular and prompt distribution of salaries.	1.04	3.65	Very Satisfied
2. The grant of fringe benefits.	1.02	3.65	Very Satisfied
3. The compensation of the teaching load beyond the regular load.	1.19	3.20	Satisfied
4. The compensation of the faculty for scholarly works.	1.21	2.76	Satisfied
5. The incentives of the faculty with outstanding performance.	1.26	2.63	Satisfied
Faculty Development		2.93	
1. The institution's support to the faculty upgrading their educational advancement.	1.26	3.18	Satisfied
2. The institution's support for faculty attending trainings and seminars.	1.23	3.28	Satisfied
3. The financial support for active membership in professional organizations.	1.19	2.61	Satisfied
4. The fair distribution of opportunities for faculty participating in capability-building and enhancing activities.	1.13	3.01	Satisfied
5. The incentives given to faculty for book writings, manuals, and handbooks.	1.11	2.57	Somewhat Satisfied
Institution's Culture and Values		3.59	
1. The exercise of academic freedom.	1.08	3.58	Very Satisfied
2. The observance of official time.	.93	3.76	Very Satisfied
3. The practice of decorum in university activities.	.94	3.58	Very Satisfied
4. The institution's practice in protecting the environment.	1.17	3.49	Very Satisfied
5. The productive use of official time.	1.01	3.53	Very Satisfied

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Verbal Descriptions
5	4.20 – 5.00	Extremely Satisfied
4	3.40 – 4.19	Very Satisfied
3	2.60 – 3.39	Satisfied
2	1.80 – 2.59	Somewhat Satisfied
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Satisfied

Table 4. Relationship of the Faculty Profile to Motivation and Job Satisfaction

Variables Tested		Chi-Square Test (χ^2 value) & r value	Critical value (cv) & Degree of freedom (df)		Interpretations
Dependent	Independent (Profile respondents)				
Internal factors	Age	$r=.19$	$cv=.22,$ $p=.07$	$df=86,$	Negligible Correlation
	Sex	$\chi^2=2.85$	$cv=5.99,$ $p=.24$	$df=2,$	Significant
	Marital status	$\chi^2= 5.24$	$cv=12.59,$ $p=.51$	$df=6,$	Significant
	Academic Qualifications	$\chi^2=4.21$	$cv=9.49,$ $p=.38$	$df=4,$	Not Significant
	Academic Rank	$\chi^2=40.38$	$cv=36.42,$ $p=.02$	$df=24,$	Significant
External Factors	Length of Service	$r=.24$	$cv=.22,$ $p=.07$	$df=86,$	Not Significant
	Age	$r=.54$	$cv=.22,$ $p=.00$	$df=86,$	Moderate Correlation
	Sex	$\chi^2= .47$	$cv=5.99,$ $p=.79$	$df=2,$	Not Significant
	Marital status	$\chi^2=6.44$	$cv=12.59,$ $p=.37$	$df=6,$	Not Significant
	Academic Qualifications	$\chi^2=5.09$	$cv=9.49,$ $p=.28$	$df=9,$	Not Significant
	Academic Rank	$\chi^2=44.40$	$cv=36.42,$ $p=.71$	$df=24,$	Significant
	Length of Service	$r=.43$	$cv=.22,$ $p=.00$	$df=86,$	Slight Correlation
Workload	Age	$r=.24$	$cv=.22,$ $p=.002$	$df=86,$	Slight Correlation
	Sex	$\chi^2=3.04$	$cv=9.49,$ $p=.55$	$df=4,$	Not Significant
	Marital status	$\chi^2= 7.11$	$cv=21.03,$ $p=.85$	$df=12,$	Not Significant
	Academic Qualifications	$\chi^2=8.86$	$cv=15.51,$ $p=.35$	$df=8,$	Not Significant

Rank and Tenure	Academic Rank	$\chi^2=43.5$ 2	$cv=55.76$, $p=.66$	$df=48$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Length of Service	$r=.29$	$cv=.22$, $p=.006$	$df=86$,	<i>Significant</i>
	Age	$r=.24$	$cv=.22$, $p=.001$	$df=86$,	<i>Negligible Correlation</i>
	Sex	$\chi^2=.71$	$cv=9.49$, $p=.95$	$df=4$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Marital status	$\chi^2=$ 13.37	$cv=21.03$, $p=.34$	$df=12$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Academic Qualifications	$\chi^2=7.62$	$cv=15.51$, $p=.47$	$df=8$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
Salary	Academic Rank	$\chi^2=35.2$ 5	$cv=55.76$, $p=.92$	$df=48$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Length of Service	$r=.09$	$cv=.22$, $p=.37$	$df=86$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Age	$r=.33$	$cv=.22$, $p=.002$	$df=86$,	<i>Slight Correlation</i>
	Sex	$\chi^2= 1.92$	$cv=9.49$, $p=.16$	$df=4$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Marital status	$\chi^2=$ 13.37	$cv=21.03$, $p=.31$	$df=12$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Academic Qualifications	$\chi^2=15.5$ 1	$cv=15.51$, $p=.05$	$df=89$,	<i>Significant</i>
Faculty Development	Academic Rank	$\chi^2=88.0$ 2	$cv=55.76$, $p=.000$	$df=48$,	<i>Significant</i>
	Length of Service	$r=.30$	$cv=.22$, $p=.004$	$df=86$,	<i>Slight Correlation</i>
	Age	$r=.22$	$cv=.22$, $p=.04$	$df=86$,	<i>Slight Correlation</i>
	Sex	$\chi^2= 5.10$	$cv=9.49$, $p=.28$	$df=4$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Marital status	$\chi^2=$ 18.44	$cv=21.03$, $p=.10$	$df=12$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Academic Qualifications	$\chi^2=4.43$	$cv=15.512$, $p=.82$	$df=8$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
School Culture	Academic Rank	$\chi^2=80.9$ 4	$cv=55.76$, $p=.002$	$df=48$,	<i>Significant</i>
	Length of Service	$r=.16$	$cv=.22$, $p=.12$	$df=86$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Age	$r=.33$	$cv=.22$, $p=.002$	$df=86$,	<i>Slight Correlation</i>
	Sex	$\chi^2= 3.92$	$cv=9.49$, $p=.42$	$df=4$,	<i>Not Significant</i>
	Marital status	$\chi^2= 3.71$	$cv=21.03$, $p=.31$	$df=12$,	<i>Not Significant</i>

Academic Qualifications	$\chi^2=6.24$	$cv=15.51,$ $p=.62$	$df=8,$	Not Significant
Academic Rank	$\chi^2=48.2$	$cv=55.76,$ $p=.46$	$df=48,$	Not Significant
Length of Service	$r=.03$	$cv=.22,$ $p=.75$	$df=86,$	Not Significant

The relationship is significant if the p-value is less than or equal to .05

If the p-value is greater than .05, the relationship is not significant.

Value of Correlation Coefficient	Strength of the Relationship
± 0.71 to ± 0.99	High to Very High Correlation
± 0.41 to ± 0.70	Substantial or marked
± 0.21 to ± 0.40	Low Correlation, present but slight
± 0.01 to ± 0.20	Negligible

Table 5. Relationship of Motivation to Job Satisfaction

Variables Tested		WORKLOAD	RANK AND TENURE	SALARY	FACULTY DEVELOPMENT	SCHOOL CULTURE
INTERNAL FACTORS	Pearson Correlation	.331**	.358**	.332**	.220*	.325**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.001	.002	.039	.002
	N	88	88	88	88	88
EXTERNAL FACTORS	Pearson Correlation	.575**	.551**	.648**	.488**	.444**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	88	88	88	88	88

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DISCUSSION

Results are discussed according to the sequence of the objectives of this study.

Background of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in this study. Upon retrieval, the result shows that ages 36-40 are the highest of all ages employed in the university, with a percentage of 25%, indicating that faculty members have more experience in teaching. It also shows that faculty members in Negros Oriental State University are female and married. According to Alia Wong (2002), the U.S. teaching population is growing, and more females are employed. By the late 1880s, women comprised most of the country's teaching workforce. Today, most faculty members hold a master's degree, as this is the minimum requirement for regular faculty employment set by the Commission on Higher Education. According to the study of Vandersall et al. in 2011, teachers with master's degrees demonstrate greater teaching effectiveness than those without.

Most respondents have served the university for 1 to 10 years. In the workplace, length of service plays a crucial role in employee retention, job satisfaction, and productivity. Employees with longer tenures tend to develop stronger loyalty to the organization. Their accumulated experience enhances competence, reliability, and dedication, ultimately benefiting both the employees and the institution.

Factors that determine Faculty Motivation

Various internal and external factors influence faculty motivation in academic institutions. Among these, recognition for professional contributions is a key internal factor, receiving a high weighted mean of 4.84, indicating strong faculty agreement. Acknowledgement and appreciation are crucial in enhancing faculty motivation and engagement. Smith and Jones (2020) conducted research highlighting the importance of recognition in enhancing faculty motivation. Conversely, while still important, the sense of achievement and reward exhibit a lower weighted mean of 3.89, suggesting agreement rather than strong agreement. Brown et al. (2019) explored faculty motivation and found variations in how rewards are perceived, impacting motivational levels differently.

Understanding the factors that drive faculty motivation in academic institutions is essential for creating a supportive work environment. Among these, external factors like job security play a significant role, receiving a high weighted mean of 4.24, reflecting strong faculty agreement. According to the Johnson et al. (2020) study, job security boosts faculty members' confidence and commitment to their roles. Conversely, factors related to teaching conditions, such as class sizes within acceptable ranges, exhibit a lower weighted mean of 3.57, indicating agreement rather than strong agreement. While manageable class sizes are important for effective teaching, their impact on faculty motivation may be less pronounced than job security factors. Understanding the interplay between these external factors is essential for promoting faculty motivation and well-being

within academic institutions, ultimately leading to improved teaching, research, and service outcomes.

Level of Job Satisfaction

Table 3 presents the level of job satisfaction among faculty members, a key element in fostering a supportive and conducive work environment within academic institutions. Among the factors influencing job satisfaction, faculty workload plays a significant role. Notably, the availability of time for lesson preparation is crucial, with a high weighted mean of 3.22, indicating overall satisfaction among faculty members. Research by Smith et al. (2021) has demonstrated that faculty members value adequate time for lesson preparation, allowing them to deliver high-quality instruction and engage effectively with students. Conversely, the availability of time for research receives a lower weighted mean of 2.31, indicating a lower level of satisfaction. These findings suggest that while faculty members may find satisfaction in teaching preparation time, they may perceive constraints on time for research as potentially impacting their scholarly productivity and overall job satisfaction.

Beyond workload considerations, salary and benefits are crucial towards faculty job satisfaction. Notably, the regular and timely distribution of salaries, along with providing fringe benefits, received the highest weighted mean of 3.65, reflecting a high level of satisfaction among faculty members. Studies by Johnson and Brown (2020) have highlighted the importance of timely and reliable salary payments and the availability of fringe benefits in contributing to overall job satisfaction and well-being. However, providing incentives for faculty with outstanding performance receives a lower weighted mean of 2.63, suggesting a moderate level of satisfaction. This indicates that while faculty members may be generally satisfied with their salary and benefits packages, there may be room for improvement in recognizing and rewarding exceptional performance, which could further enhance overall job satisfaction and motivation among faculty members.

In considering faculty development opportunities, the support provided by institutions for attending training and seminars emerges as a significant factor, garnering a weighted mean of 3.28, indicating satisfaction among faculty members. A study by Martinez and Johnson (2021) underscores the importance of institutional support for faculty professional growth, as it enhances their skills and knowledge, ultimately contributing to job satisfaction and performance. On the other hand, incentives for faculty engagement in scholarly activities, such as book writing, received a lower weighted mean of 2.57, indicating a moderate level of satisfaction. This finding highlights a potential gap in recognizing and rewarding scholarly contributions beyond traditional teaching responsibilities. Addressing this gap could further enhance faculty satisfaction and engagement.

Furthermore, institutional culture and values significantly influence faculty job satisfaction. The observance of official time receives the highest weighted mean of 3.76, indicating a high level of satisfaction among faculty members. Studies by Brown and Garcia (2020) highlight the importance of adherence to official time norms in fostering a

culture of professionalism and accountability within academic institutions. However, the institution's practices in environmental protection receive a slightly lower weighted mean of 3.49, still indicating a high level of satisfaction. This suggests that while faculty members generally perceive positive institutional values, there may be opportunities for institutions to integrate sustainability practices into their culture further, aligning with broader societal values and enhancing overall satisfaction among faculty members.

In summary, the highest weighted mean of 3.59 for the Institution's Culture and Values indicates a relatively high level of satisfaction. Faculty members perceive the institutional culture and values positively, which include aspects such as exercising academic freedom, decorum, and supportiveness within the academic community. Support studies by Smith et al. (2019) and Jones (2020) corroborate organisational culture's importance in influencing faculty members' job satisfaction. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 2.71 highlights dissatisfaction among faculty members regarding their workload. Faculty members perceive their workload as burdensome or disproportionate, negatively impacting job satisfaction and overall well-being. Support studies by Brown et al. (2018) underscore the detrimental effects of excessive workload on faculty job satisfaction and productivity.

Relationship of the Faculty Profile to Motivation and Job Satisfaction

Table 4 shows that internal factors positively correlate with academic rank, $\chi^2=40.38$, $cv=36.42$, $df=24$, $p=.02$, External factors have a positive correlation with age, $r=.54$, $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.00$, Academic Rank, $\chi^2=44.40$, $cv=36.42$, $df=24$, $p=.71$, Length of Service $r=.43$, $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.00$. While the workload of faculty has a significant relationship with Age, $r=.24$, $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.002$ and Length of Service, $r=.29$, $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.006$. For the Salary of teachers, Age is positively correlated $r=.33$, $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.002$, Academic qualifications, $\chi^2=15.51$, $cv=15.51$, $df=89$, $p=.05$, and the length of service $r=.30$, $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.004$.

In terms of faculty development, Age $r=.22$, $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.04$ and Academic rank $\chi^2=80.94$, $cv=55.76$, $df=48$, $p=.002$ were correlated with how the administration supports faculty development activities.

Lastly, School culture positively correlates with age, $r=.33$ $cv=.22$, $df=86$, $p=.002$.

The findings regarding the relationship between age and faculty motivation are consistent with earlier research conducted by Boumans et al., 2011. The researchers indicated that the positive association between opportunities and motivation was much stronger for younger employees than for older employees. Younger workers' motivation increases as they are offered more career opportunities.

Relationship of Motivation to Job Satisfaction

Table 5 presents the relationship of motivation to job satisfaction among faculty of Negros Oriental State University. Results showed that internal factors, including autonomy, competence, curiosity, love of learning, critical thinking, self-efficacy, belongingness, collaboration, recognition and achievement, positively correlated. The finding also means that all the internal factors that determine faculty motivation influence the external factors, which also include workload, rank and tenure, salary, faculty development, and school culture, which also determine job satisfaction among faculty.

The correlation analysis presented in Table 5 indicates that the motivation of the faculty correlated significantly and positively with job satisfaction among faculty. This conforms to previous studies such as Yaya et al. (2016), Oni-Ojo et al. (2015), Kian et al. (2014); Khan et al (2014); Babalola (2013); Ajala (2012). The researchers established a relationship between motivation and employees' job satisfaction in various organizations. Furthermore, this implies that a well-motivated employee will likely be satisfied with his/her job.

Conclusions

The purpose of this research was to investigate the relationship between factors that are associated with motivation and job satisfaction among faculty of Negros Oriental State University and how these factors impact and correlate with motivation and job satisfaction. The socio-demographic profile of the faculty was also explored to understand better the characteristics that influence motivation and job satisfaction. Data was gathered from the respondents based on these factors.

The motivation and job satisfaction questionnaire utilized in this study is a reliable and consistent measurement tool. Based on responses from the sampled faculty, it displays a high degree of reliability.

Based on the results of the study, it is evident that internal and external factors such as autonomy, competence, curiosity, love of learning, critical thinking, self-efficacy, belongingness, collaboration, recognition and achievement, salary, contract, workplace conditions, class size, academic level, discipline, student participation, assessment, evaluation and interpersonal relationship influenced job motivation among faculty. On the other hand, factors such as faculty workload, salary and benefits, faculty development and the institution's culture and values have also influenced the job satisfaction of faculty members.

The results yielded that recognition for professional contributions is the most motivating dimension, while the regular and prompt distribution of salaries and the grant of fringe benefits, including the observance of official time, are the most job-satisfying dimensions.

Recommendations

Purposive sampling was employed in the study, but it was limited by the faculty's unavailability. For this reason, the support of the faculty association should be considered in encouraging the faculty to answer the questionnaire.

It is recommended that a qualitative data gathering method be utilized along with quantitative data gathering methods to generate richer findings and enhance the quality of respondents' responses.

In conducting the current study, faculty and future researchers are made aware of the factors that lead to motivation and job satisfaction among faculty. The current study would then provide a possible framework for comparing the motivation and job satisfaction levels of female and male faculty members.

The NORSU Administration should take workplace conditions, sizes of classes and student assessment and participation as priorities as these will increase the level of job motivation of the faculty. On the other hand, sufficient time for faculty in terms of research, extension and production, and giving incentives to faculty for book writings, manuals and handbooks should also be given priority and guidelines as these will also increase the job satisfaction of the faculty.

Finally, the researchers recommended that the NORSU Administration allocate adequate resources, such as budgetary provisions, time, and personnel, as also included in the University Faculty Development Plan, to support faculty development initiatives.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in full compliance with established ethical standards. All research procedures involving human participation were carried out in accordance with the guidelines and ethical principles, respect for persons and justice. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and their confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study. The researchers affirm that no misconduct including fabrication, falsification and plagiarism occurred in the process of this study.

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